

Studies in "Photo-sols." Part I.

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Freundlich and Nathansohn (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1921, 29, 16) while experimenting on the interaction of similarly charged sols, observed the formation of silver sulphide in the reaction between sulphur sol (prepared according to Weirman and Oden) and silver sol (according to Lea's method). In the reaction between arsenic trisulphide sol and silver sol, the formation of a compound of silver, arsenic and sulphur was observed whose composition was not determined. Both reactions were accompanied by a series of characteristic colour changes.

A closer study of the interaction of the arsenic trisulphide sol (prepared according to Lea's method) is made by Freundlich and Moore (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1925, 36, 17). The reaction taking place in the dark is distinguished from that taking place in light. In dark the original colour of the mixture changes into greenish brown with no further change for weeks over, whereas in light further colour changes ensue and the final colour becomes golden yellow.

The present work is an extension of the above and the authors have tried to investigate how the mixture of arsenic trisulphide sol would behave under different conditions of light, air and concentration with a view to get the mixture which is most sensitive to light and also to find the most effective spectral region. Further the phenomenon of colour changes observed in the interaction of silver sol and antimony trisulphide sol has been studied as also the reaction between gold sol and the two sulphide sols.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Sols.

The hydrosol of silver was prepared by Bredig's method using a current of two amperes. Its concentration was determined by Volhard's method. The hydrosols of arsenic and antimony trisulphides were prepared by passing hydrogen sulphide through solutions of arsenious oxide and potassium antimony tartrate respectively and then removing the free hydrogen sulphide by bubbling hydrogen. Their concentrations were determined by coagulating them by dilute

hydrochloric acid and weighing the coagulæ as trisulphides. The gold sol was prepared by Zsigmondy's method of reducing gold chloride by formaldehyde and also by Bredig's method. The concentration was determined in the latter case by a colorimetric device. The strengths of the different colloidal solutions used in the following experiments are given below :—

Name of the sol.	Weight of the substance per litre.
Ag Sol No. I	0·0995 gms.
Ag Sol No. II (protected in gelatine)	0·3682
Ag Sol No. III	0·1742
Ag Sol No. IV	0·06694
Ag Sol No. V	0·10087
As ₂ S ₃ Sol No. I	1·8440
As ₂ S ₃ Sol No. II	1·980
Sb ₂ S ₃ Sol No. I	0·290
Sb ₂ S ₃ Sol No. II	0·530
Au Sol No. I (Zsigmondy's method)	0·05384
Au Sol No. II (Bredig's method)	0·09423
Au Sol No. III (do)	0·004615

Reaction of the metallic sols with the sulphide sols and the effect of light and air on the interaction.

To study this phenomenon four mixtures having the two ingredients in the same proportion (which is shown in the following tables) were prepared. One was exposed to light only, the second to air only, the third to both light and air and the fourth to neither. Changes of colour in slow stages are observed to take place when the mixtures are exposed to light or to both light and air and no change is undergone in darkness excepting a slight immediate darkening of the colour of the mixture as soon as it is made. It is this darkened colour that is regarded as the initial colour of the mixture in the following tables which show the general results of experiments.

Interaction of Silver Sol and Arsenic Trisulphide Sol.

Constituents of the mixtures.	No. of different sets of mixtures.	Proportion of the two sols in c. cs. in the mixtures.		Colour changes in slow stages when exposed to light or both light and air.		Changes in dark both when exposed to air and when not.
		Ag sol.	As ₂ S ₃ sol.	Initial colour.	Final colour.	
A. As ₂ S ₃ sol No. I and Ag sol No. I.	(1)	10	10	Blackish green.	Yellow in 4½ hours.	No change in 24 hours and over two weeks.
	(2)	12	10			
	(3)	10	12			
	(4)	14	9			
B. As ₂ S ₃ sol No. II and Ag sol No. I.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.
C. Ag sol No. II and As ₂ S ₃ sol No. I.	(1)	10	10	Dark bluish yellow.	No well marked change in colour in 24 hrs. The mixtures coagulate.	No change excepting coagulation in case of mixtures No. 2 and No. 3 which commenced as soon as they were made.
	(2)	8	10			
	(3)	10	14			
	(4)	8	14			
D. Ag sol No. II and As ₂ S ₃ sol No. II.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.

Qualitative Chemical Analysis.

This was done in case of those mixtures which underwent a colour change in light. The method followed in this and the following cases was to coagulate the colloidal particles in the final mixtures by exhaustive cataphoresis. The clear solution and the precipitate thus formed were separated from each other and each examined by the usual analytical methods.

In the present case the investigation consisted in finding as to what new compound or compounds were formed whose constituents would be two or more from among As, Ag, S, and O—the elements participating in the reaction.

Formation of arsenious acid was detected in the clear liquid and of silver sulphide and free sulphur in the precipitate.

Interaction of Silver Sol and Antimony Trisulphide Sol.

Constituents of the mixtures.	No. of different sets of mixtures.	Proportion of the two sols in c. cs. in the mixtures.		Colour changes in slow stages when exposed to light or both light and air.		Changes in darkness whether exposed to air or not.
		Sb ₂ S ₃ sol.	Ag sol.	Initial colour.	Final colour.	
A. Ag sol No. I and Sb ₂ S ₃ sol No. I.	(1)	10	10	Dark with a shade of orange red.	Orange red in 7 hrs.	No change.
	(2)	12	10			
	(3)	10	12			
	(4)	9	14			
B. Ag sol No. V and Sb ₂ S ₃ sol No. I.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Orange red in 12 hrs.	Do.
C. Ag sol No. II and Sb ₂ S ₃ sol No. I.	Do.	Do.	Do.	No well-marked change. The initial blackishness undergoes a slight decrease.		No change.
D. Ag Sol No. II and Sb ₂ S ₃ sol No. II.	Do.	Do.	Do.	The initial colour of the mixtures darkens a little. There is a tendency towards coagulation which increases with the increase of Sb ₂ S ₃ sol in the mixture.		No change except that mixture No. III coagulates.

Qualitative chemical analysis was done in case of the final mixtures in the combinations of those sols that exhibited a characteristic colour change (in A and B).

Formation of antimonious acid, silver sulphide and free sulphur was detected.

Interaction of Gold Sols and Arsenic Trisulphide Sol.

Preliminary experiments showed that there was little effect of diffused light on the mixture of the above two sols. Sunlight however had an appreciable effect. Exposure to light in the following tables stands for exposure to sun-light.

Constituents of the mixtures.	No. of different sets of mixtures.	Proportion of the two sols in c.c.s. in the mixtures.		Colour changes when exposed to light and when to both light and air.		Changes in darkness when exposed to air and when not.
		Au sol.	As ₂ S ₃ sol.	Initial colour.	Final colour.	
A. Au sol No. II and As ₂ S ₃ sol No. I.	(1)	10	10	Green	Yellow-green.	No change.
	(2)	10	6.3	Green with a slight dark shade.	Violet with a greenish yellow shade.	
	(3)	6.3	10	Yellowish green.	Yellow with greenish shade.	
	(4)	16	7	Dark green.	Violet.	
B. Au sol No. II and As ₂ S ₃ sol No. I.	(1)	12	12	The initial colour is bluish green or blue according as the proportion of Au sol is less or more than As ₂ S ₃ sol and the final colour is accordingly blue or indigo after an exposure of 14 hours.		Do.
	(2)	12	8			
	(3)	8	12			
	(4)	16	12			
C. Au sol No. II and As ₂ S ₃ sol No. I.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.

Note :—The final colours are acquired by the mixtures in A above in 7 hours.

Qualitative chemical analysis of the final mixtures was done in the same way as in the previous cases. Formation of gold sulphide, free sulphur and arsenious acid was detected.

The colour changes accompanying the interaction of Au sol No. II and As_2S_3 sol No. I and Au sol No. II and As_2S_3 sol No. II were observed at intervals by means of Nutting's spectro-photometer. The general result in both cases was that the absorption capacity for light of all sets of mixtures became less and less with the increase in the exposure to light.

Interaction of Gold Sol and Antimony Trisulphide.

Constituents of the mixtures.	No. of different sets of mixtures.	Proportion of the two in the mixture in c.cs.		Changes of colour in slow stages when exposed to light only and when to both light and air.		Time to acquire the final colour.
		Au sol.	Sb_2S_3 sol.	Initial colour.	Final colour.	
A. Au sol No. I and Sb_2S_3 sol No. II.	(1)	10	10	Darkish orange.	Brownish orange.	6 hours.
	(2)	12	8	Darkish orange.	Orange with violet shade.	
	(3)	8	12	Dark.	Orange.	
	(4)	18	8	Dark orange.	Violet brown.	
B. Au sol No. II and Sb_2S_3 sol No. I.	(1)	12	12	Blackish orange.	Black.	14 hours.
	(2)	12	7	Do.	Blackish blue.	
	(3)	7	12	Orange slightly black.	Brownish black.	
	(4)	16	8	Orange black.	Black with a faint blue shade.	
C. Au sol No. II and Sb_2S_3 sol No. II	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.

As usual no change of colour was noticed in case of mixtures placed in dark.

Qualitative analysis conducted in the same way as before showed the formation of antimonious acid, free sulphur and gold sulphide.

Interaction of Sb_2S_3 sol No. I and Au sol No. III and of Au sol No. III and Sb_2S_3 sol II was followed at intervals by noting the colour changes by means of Nutting's spectro-photometer. The general changes in both cases was the increase in transparency of the mixture with the increase of exposure.

Conclusion.

The photo-sensitive nature of the reaction between silver sol (prepared by Lea's method) was discovered by Freundlich and Nathansohn. The foregoing experiments lead us to conclude that no alteration in this respect takes place in the behaviour of the silver sol, if prepared by Bredig's method. Further we are in a position to say that the reaction between the silver sol and the antimony trisulphide sol is likewise photo-chemical, though slower, so far as colour changes are concerned.

As mentioned in the introduction, the mixture of gold sol and arsenic trisulphide sol was regarded by Freundlich and Nathansohn as indifferent towards light. The present work corroborates this observation with respect to the effect of diffused light, with this addition that the mixture is influenced by the light of the sun, and the interaction in sunlight is also accompanied by colour changes. The interaction between gold sol and antimony trisulphide sol is also discovered to be photo-chemical and likewise attended by changes of colour.

Chemical examination of the mixtures when they had attained the final colour reveals the formation of the sulphide of the metal, free sulphur and antimonious or arsenious acid (according as antimony trisulphide or arsenic trisulphide sol was used).

Theory of the Change.

Initially we had the mixture of the metal sol (Ag or Au) and the sulphide sol (As_2S_3 or Sb_2S_3) and after exposure when there was no further change of colour in light, presence of the metal sulphide, free sulphur and the acid (arsenious or antimonious) was detected in the mixture. The change can be explained by considering the sulphide sol to hydrolyse into the acid and H_2S . H_2S can yield

H₂O and S by the action of air and light. This accounts for the presence of free sulphur. H₂S may react with the colloidal particles of the metal to form its sulphide. The several stages or the different extents to which the reactions proceed would correspond to different states of colour exhibited by the mixture.

Svedberg and other workers in their recent photographic investigations on the nature of "latent image" (cf. "Photo-electricity" by Stanley, Ed. 1925, pp. 256-257) postulate the existence of certain sensitization centres in the grain of the photographic film; again F. C. Toy assumes that such centres are particles which are not silver halide. Further Henry and Sheppard account for the high sensitivity of the film by the presence of nuclei of Ag₂S, which according to them contaminate it. Theories regarding the sensitizing action of silver sulphide differ (*vide Journal of the Society of Chemical Industry*, Supplement, March, 1926, p. 219). These theories have direct bearing on our subject. We can likewise postulate that the small quantities of the metal sulphide formed initially in the mixtures of the sols form the centres of photo-chemical sensitivity and accelerate the chemical changes which are accompanied by the corresponding manifestations of colour.

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